

GOVERNING A JUST NET ZERO TRANSITION

The Bristol Toolkit and City and Community Visions for Change

JOEL TERWILLIGER | NET ZERO FUTURES BRIEF SERIES NO.3 OF 5

RESEARCH FOCUS AND POLICY CONTEXT

Cities need not only ambitious strategies but practical decision-support tools to navigate the lived realities, complexities, paradoxes, and tensions between pressure to accelerate emissions reductions whilst building inclusive mandates for change, without additional resources for either. Bristol has put just transition as its north star and advanced both UK and EU thinking around justice-centric governance design. Participation in the EU Cities Mission alongside UK-funded community climate work has produced a distinctive toolkit spanning the public, knowledge and advisory, and VCSE sectors. This brief asks a commonly overlooked question: amidst different actor orientations, which tools add practical value, which remain aspirational, and how are they—or aren't they—shaping each other and wider policymaking?

KEY FINDINGS

The Bristol toolkit clarifies just transition elements needed: the city's leadership role and interconnected enablers; multi-lens appraisal; and a vision for city-VCSE powered enabling ecosystems. The Climate City Contract (CCC) plots a 2030 roadmap with a socioeconomic lens; the Community Climate Action Plans (CCAPs) ground solutions in citizens' lived experience; and Community investment planning and Leadership Panel mechanisms mark first steps toward a multi-level, shared theory of change. Yet all are bottom-up experiments in a context of no national-to-local framework and a competitive funding landscape that incentivises bringing new tools to the 'marketplace of ideas' rather than build on, align, or co-refine existing ones. Bristol's CCC and 17 CCAPs reveal common ground but also diverging visions for change. The gap is institutional, relational, and political—the cost of aligning tools and systems without a structured, nested model risks increased complexity without strengthened collective action and learning.

KEY MESSAGES FOR POLICY AND PRACTICE

- **Establish a National Net Zero Community Action Framework.** VCSEs surface priorities — resilience, social inclusion, wellbeing — that city and regional planning systems struggle to absorb: existing monitoring systems lack the methods to define and scale just transition metrics. A consistent impact taxonomy and monitoring guidance would help bridge that gap, enabling community-defined value to genuinely inform city and regional strategies.
- **Address inverted funding incentives that reward producing new tools over aligning existing ones.** Most decision-support tools remain largely conceptual and disconnected from practical city needs, driving cities to create their own. Build incentives for framework holders and designers to collaborate — aligning and co-refining existing tools where possible — rather than compete.
- **Bristol's toolkit is a compass with just transition as its north star — each tool orients toward the same destination but with different approaches to getting there.** Deliberate, long-term feedback loops are needed to ensure diverse community and stakeholder visions actively co-create city strategy priorities and interventions rather than sit alongside it.
- **Community Climate Action Plans are a starting point for seeding project pipelines, not investible propositions.** Structuring community priorities so they can connect to city and regional investment plans requires intentional governance — mechanisms like the Community Leadership Panel and Community Climate Action Prospectus offer promising routes.

PART 1: CROSS-SECTOR DECISION-SUPPORT TOOLS

Brief 1 outlined Procedural Governance Tools (PGTs) as the structured approaches that shape how decisions are made, actors are engaged, and policies are implemented. While PGTs tend to be more narrowly conceived as specific mechanisms (advisory committees) or outputs (climate strategies), a closely related but even less-studied category is equally important: the decision-support tools that help city officers, knowledge actors, and community anchor organisations (CAOs) focus and prioritise enabling actions across innovation domains. Bristol's approach to governing a just transition is informed by an evolving suite of decision-support tools aimed at integrating place-based innovation across governance, financial, community, and systems dimensions. The NZF study traced how these tools emerged across sectors, each bringing distinct logics and capabilities to the shared challenge of net zero transformation.

Figure 1 captures the relational logic underlying the Bristol case as a whole: social innovation (stakeholder involvement and community-led planning) combines with learning innovation (impact assessment and learning systems) and financial innovation (the finance lab and its mandate-integrating work) to drive governance innovation—the alignment and scalability goals that together constitute the enabling system for net zero transformation. The key focus of the Community Climate Action (BCNP, no date a) and Mission Net Zero (BCC, 2023a) projects was to design and test CAO-led co-production and engagement processes that open strategic planning to people and insights that haven't traditionally been engaged, while creating feedback loops to influence strategic climate action and investment priorities at the city and regional, and ultimately national, levels.

Figure 1. Innovation Types Applied to the Bristol Innovation Ecosystem. Own Illustration.

This intersectionality of innovation aims to create different ways of working, broaden the number of actors beyond the city, and bring new insights traditionally not considered as 'evidence-based.' Mechanisms like the Community Leadership Panel (BCNP, no date b) brought CAO representatives with lived experience—whose expertise isn't as valued in formal processes—into the strategic planning sphere to input and represent local voices. At the same time, efforts to link community-led action plans with the Bristol CCC (BCC, 2024) and regional investment planning (WECA, 2025b) built momentum towards a more shared theory of change.

These activities map directly onto the **REPAIR** dimensions (Terwilliger and Christie, 2025)

introduced in **Brief 1: Participatory and Enabling/Embedding** (co-production and community leadership processes); **Integrative** (aligning city and community PGTs); both **Reflexivity** and **Adaptive** (learning from shared ways of working and collective-intelligence); and **Radicality** (asking who defines success and on whose terms).

Together, they raise a key question: How can these efforts be aligned as 'pieces of the jigsaw'—creating a shared theory of change, influencing how net zero creates local benefits, and navigating tensions over who is responsible for what?

Public Sector Decision-Support Tools

The Four-Lens Model for Place-Based Innovation

The Four-Lens Model, as explained by one city officer, outlines the sensemaking lenses for Bristol's integrated approach to place-based net zero governance innovation (shown in Table 1). It frames intervention or governance decision considerations through four simultaneous analytical perspectives: **institutional** (governance structures, mandates, and accountability mechanisms); **market** (financial instruments, investment logic, and business model design); **community** (lived experience, equity, and co-production); and **systems** (cross-sectoral alignment around value propositions/portfolios, clean energy scenarios/learning loops, and long-

term change dynamics). The model's power lies in its insistence that effective governance of a just transition cannot be reduced to any single logic—and that a balanced, holistic approach to the realities of a rapidly evolving change environment is needed, particularly in terms of growing opposition and misinformation around net zero. The model's limitations lie in its breadth: with four lenses to navigate simultaneously, there is a risk of treating alignment as a conceptual exercise rather than a sustained governance investment requiring dedicated resources.

Table 1

Bristol's Four-Lens Model for Integrating Place-Based Innovation Approaches

Lens	Innovation Alignments	REPAIR Dimensions	Strategic Significance
Community Perspective	Social, Governance	Participatory, Integrative	Grounds strategic decisions in resident needs. Ensures interventions are human-centric, equitable, and politically viable by mitigating the risk of social backlash.
Energy Planning Perspective	Learning, Governance	Integrative, Adaptive	Provides the technical, data-driven analysis necessary to plot decarbonisation pathway scenarios. Acts as a continuous feedback loop for feasibility and refining strategy.
Asset Owners & Actors Perspective	Financial, Governance	Enabling/ Embedding, Integrative	Maps the financial and operational landscape, identifying who holds capital and assets, and what their routes to funding are, thereby enabling a blended financial approach.
Investment Readiness Perspective	Financial, Governance, Learning	Radicality, Reflexivity	Transforms diverse projects into 'investable buckets,' a radical departure from traditional models designed to unlock private/national capital by structuring acceptable risk profiles while ensuring public value outcome criteria are met.

Bristol's 'Tripod' Approach to Net Zero Delivery: Demand, Supply, Finance, and Data

At the operational level, the NZF study identifies how Bristol frames its approach (Figure 2, adapted from (BCC, 2023b, 2025c)) to enabling net zero delivery across three interconnected enablers powered by data—each corresponding to a dimension of the challenge that governance and finance tools must address. **Demand** activation focuses on stimulating the willingness and ability of people to act, understanding what communities want—

particularly the often marginalised—and distributing benefits fairly. **Supply** support addresses the capacity of the supply chain (including skills and workforce) to deliver at the required scale and pace. **Finance** innovation concentrates on closing the finance gap via a portfolio approach and innovative blended finance models. All three are supported by Data—the basis for good decision-making across domains.

Figure 2. Bristol's 'Tripod' Approach to Net Zero Delivery.

This framework is significant because it positions the net zero delivery challenge as a set of interconnected systemic enablers that must be developed together. Demand without finance leaves communities with unfunded aspirations; finance without supply creates investment pipelines without workforce capacity; data without demand risks optimising for the wrong outcomes. Each enabler requires different actors and governance mechanisms, and the city cannot deliver the transition alone.

Bristol's City Governance Roles: The Climate Action Change Pyramid

The Climate Action Change Pyramid (Figure 3, adapted from (BCNP, 2025c; Urban Foresight, 2025)) frames the distinct layers at which the city acts to enable a just transition. The pyramid articulates four layers of climate action leadership, from the foundation upward, each associated with a distinct role for cities to fulfil to accelerate change.

Figure 3. Bristol's Climate Action Change Pyramid: Layers of City Leadership.

At the foundation, decarbonising the council's own operations requires **Direct Control**—leading by example and getting the city's 'own house in order.' Delivering services that decarbonise the city requires an **Influencing** role: place-shaping and leadership to innovate on service delivery. Enabling partners to decarbonise calls for **Convening**—ensuring support structures are available and embedded using iterative, design-led approaches. At the outermost layer, supporting citizens to change requires **Bridging**: aligning strategic and investment planning with just transition principles by ensuring community voices actively shape decision-making

and removing or not exacerbating barriers through consciously designing towards fairness. This pyramid makes the city's role in a just transition explicit: to actively bridge between institutional planning and community priorities, using its convening power to create conditions in which community knowledge shapes policy, rather than simply being an add-on to interventions after they are designed. The NZF study finds this bridging role is where Bristol has made the most progress—and where the most fragile dependencies on individual champions and project-based funding remain.

Knowledge and Advisory Sector Decision-Support Tools

A key intent of financial innovation models explored across the UK and EU support ecosystems is to foster systemic change: not just financing change but changing finance. This change was envisioned by experts in both NZC and Net Zero Living (NZL) programmes as progressing investment models that generate community-level social value rather than being primarily extractive.

Knowledge and advisory partners—including consultancies, research institutes, and NZC platform experts—support cities with a suite of tools designed to structure financial innovation activities: developing investable propositions, aligning mandates across governance levels, and making the case for net zero action to attract multi-stakeholder collective action and private actor investment.

The NetZeroCities ‘Multi-Approach’ to Unlocking Alternative Net Zero Finance

One such framework was articulated as the NZC ‘Multi-Approach’ to unlocking alternative net zero finance: multi-actor (diverse perspectives): multi-instrument (broadening the toolbox), and; multi-level (considering various governance scales) (DML, BwB and South Pole, 2025). Through strategic advocacy for changes that are not under the city’s direct control and strategic selection (best use) of policy powers that are, cities can ‘be systemic and get specific’ and find

ways to unlock alternative funding. Cities advocate for and use multiple instruments (shown in [Table 2](#)), together “in service of a city mission.” This market-centric framing is focused on market fixing, shaping, and making, with city shaping through information and convening instruments, primarily via engaging specific stakeholders (vs. wider citizen engagement): property/business owners, insurers, policymakers, and utilities.

Table 2

Instruments in the NZC ‘Multi-Approach’ to Unlocking Alternative Net Zero Finance

Legislative & Regulatory	Financial	Information & Convening
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Licensing & permits - Mandated standards - Other - Procurement policies - Quotas & caps - Zoning & land use regulations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Direct / indirect taxation - Grants - Loans & loan guarantees - Other - Subsidies - Tax incentives / incentive schemes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Education & training programmes / public awareness campaigns - Data & research dissemination / public information & metrics - Plans & strategies - Procedures, guidelines, protocols - Public consultations & stakeholder engagement - Voluntary standards

The Net Zero Living Programme: The Net Zero Neighbourhood Model

A key issue with financial innovation models that blend public and private funds is that the tension between public value and private returns creates a severe alignment challenge: community regeneration interventions that are inherently non-revenue generating, while the city must package projects that satisfy the return-on-investment criteria of private financiers. The Net Zero Neighbourhood (NZN) Model (3Ci, 2023)—developed through the NZL programme and explored in the Bristol Lab—represents efforts to create and test a replicable, place-based delivery framework that integrates community-led

planning with city- and regional-level investment by taking a regeneration approach to scaling housing retrofits. With potential for scaling into a national programme structure, the NZN model bundles disruptive carbon mitigation work (solar PV, insulation, heat pumps) with community infrastructure upgrades (waste/active travel solutions, green spaces), generating buy-in via localised quality-of-life improvements.

The persistent challenge identified in the NZF study is that multiple elements are needed over and above financing models and additional private finance: systemic, flexible technical assistance and project development funding; resources for dedicated, embedded research and advocacy to support local governance and community engagement; and shared frameworks that

policies that simultaneously address climate and cost-of-living crises to realise co-benefits for communities. Siloed governance and support structures create alignment gaps at the point of delivery. Some key dimensions, issues, and implications the NZN model was designed to address, as explained by one of its key architects, are outlined in [Table 3](#).

Table 3

The Net Zero Neighbourhood (NZN) Model: Policy Dimensions, Issues, and Implications

Policy Dimension	Issue	Rationale/Implication
Net Zero Polarisation / Pushback	Net zero as a policy frame does not resonate with much of the UK population, as political debate over recent years has shown.	Selling change on net zero grounds alone risks public resistance. The NZN model leads with local, visible benefits rather than policy compliance.
Inequalities Inbuilt into UK Housing Stock	Dramatic inequalities in housing quality—heat efficiency, damp, mould—have direct public health consequences disproportionately borne by lower-income households.	Addressing net zero in housing simultaneously addresses entrenched health and inequality—but only if interventions are designed to reach those most affected, not just the most financially efficient.
Neighbourhood Regeneration as Mitigation & Adaptation	A focus on emissions reduction alone leaves communities unprepared for a hotter, wetter future.	Regeneration of streets and green space serves both mitigation and adaptation. The NZN model integrates both rather than treating them as separate programmes.
Think Systemically and Make Change Visible	Piecemeal, sequential infrastructure interventions—digging up streets multiple times for separate programmes—waste money, frustrate residents, and miss opportunities for visible change.	Doing it once, systemically, reduces cost and disruption, and creates the visible external signals that build public confidence in the transition.
From Single- to Multi-Measure Design	Non-revenue-generating regeneration measures—green infrastructure, community space, transport improvements—cost money that retrofit alone cannot recover.	Combining retrofit with wider regeneration creates a stronger investment story, addresses multiple imperatives simultaneously, and makes the full co-benefits case.

Voluntary, Community & Social Enterprise Sector Decision-Support Tools

Developed through the Community Climate Action (CCA) Project—a National Lottery-funded initiative supporting 17 community organisations to co-produce Community Climate Action Plans (CCAPs) with residents—Bristol's VCSE sector has developed its own suite of accompanying decision-support tools. The CCAP represents a key community-level development: a structured governance tool that makes visible the priorities and visions for change of communities that formal

city planning processes have historically struggled to incorporate. Whereas the CCC is a city-level PGT designed to align institutional, financial, and sectoral interventions around a 2030 net zero roadmap, CCAPs are community-level PGTs designed to surface community knowledge, build local ownership, and create investible propositions from the ground up. CCAPs reflect a fundamentally different starting point: not the carbon and investment logics of the CCC, but the health, wellbeing, equity, and community resilience priorities of residents. They form the basis for further co-creation and, for a number of organisations, for exploring a Community Climate Investment Plan (CCIP) mechanism with city and regional partners (examined in [Brief 4](#)).

The Community Climate and Nature Action Model

The Community Climate and Nature Action Model (BCNP, 2025b) is an ecosystem-level theory of change that places the VCSE sector at the centre of Bristol's place-based climate governance—not solely as a channel for city-designed programmes but as a trusted partner with distinctive capabilities that public institutions lack. The model (shown in Figure 4) builds on an asset-based community development approach: starting from what CAOs already know,

care about, and do—and asking how these strengths can be connected to wider climate strategy. Its ecosystem conditions include a place-based climate action network, a supportive and engaged local authority, strong community anchor organisations, climate and nature expert advice, funding and resources, and a collaborative approach across sectors.

Figure 4. The Community Climate and Nature Action Model: Bristol's Replicable Place-based Ecosystem.

The model emphasises building a critical mass of 'non-climate-specialist' community leaders—people with deep local knowledge and trusted relationships with residents—who can translate climate priorities into locally meaningful action and bring community insights back into city and regional strategy. This explicitly challenges the deficit model common in urban climate governance, where communities are positioned as passive recipients of expert-driven technical knowledge. The model encompasses insight across 17 CAO organisations, spanning geographical (specific Bristol neighbourhoods), demographic (disability, ethnicity, age), and shared interest (artists, cricketers) communities—representing a diversity of lived experiences that enrich and enhance city governance processes.

The Just Transition in Action Model

The Just Transition in Action Model (Figure 5), developed through VCSE-led work in the Innovate UK funded Bristol Mission Net Zero project, builds on the Bristol Just Transition Declaration spearheaded by a group of climate advocates (Geen et al., 2024). It synthesises insights from the CCA Project, the Bristol Climate & Nature Partnership (BCNP), and wider just transition expertise from the Bristol Mission Net Zero Inclusion Associate (BCC, 2025a; Reid and BCNP, 2025).

Figure 5. The Just Transition in Action Model: Four Principles, Four Intersecting Practices.

Its four interdependent core principles (defined in Table 4)—Equity, Accessibility, Inclusivity, and Empowerment—are expressed through four intersecting practices: bridging, balancing, unlocking, and elevating. **Bridging** connects vulnerable groups to net zero opportunities through targeted pathways. **Balancing** transforms economic systems through financial inclusion to reduce inequalities in net zero benefits. **Unlocking** gives people often overlooked both access and tools to take charge of their own futures. **Elevating** ensures diverse voices not just attend decision-making processes

but that their input actually shapes outcomes and leads to meaningful change. The model's principles and practices point to dynamics that undermine just transition principles in governance practice—tokenistic engagement, equity as an afterthought, and community organisations as delivery vehicles rather than governance partners (doing to/extracting value vs. doing with). This work culminated in an inclusion in action toolkit (BCNP and Reid, 2026) to support cities in embedding these principles into multi-stakeholder innovation project design.

Table 4
Just Transition in Action Model Principles Defined

Principle	Definition
Accessibility	The identification, visibility, and prioritisation of the most vulnerable groups to ensure opportunities, services, and resources related to the net zero transition are available irrespective of background or circumstance.
Empowerment	The provision of genuine agency, ownership, and a voice to marginalised communities in the creation and implementation of net zero solutions, transforming passive recipients into active change-makers within the transition.
Equity	The active reduction of systemic inequalities, acknowledging that people start from different positions. Equity ensures that net zero actions distribute benefits and costs fairly, with specific focus on prioritising communities facing the greatest disadvantages from the transition.
Inclusivity	The democratisation of decision-making processes that ensures diverse voices, particularly those traditionally excluded, contribute meaningfully to shaping our net zero future. Inclusivity creates systems where power is shared and decisions are made collaboratively.

PART 2: SYNTHESISING CITY AND COMMUNITY VISIONS FOR CHANGE

The Bristol CCC (BCC, 2024) and the 17 CCAPs (BCNP, no date a) represent Bristol's primary city- and community-level planning tools for identifying shared priorities, articulating theories of change, and progressing Bristol's mission-oriented net zero work (described in [Box 1](#)). Both are innovations at their respective scales, embedding sophisticated thinking about co-

benefits and theories of change: the CCC engaging stakeholders across formal and informal governance structures to co-develop a new climate action and investment roadmap, the CCAP pioneering community-led co-production, grounded in the priorities and lived experience of neighbourhoods and communities.

Box 1. Two PGTs, Two Scales: Processes Behind Bristol's City and Community Plans

City Level: The Bristol Climate City Contract

Bristol's CCC emerged from a mature governance process built up over successive iterations of the One City Plan—a shared strategic framework developed through One City thematic boards covering climate, health, economy, and other cross-cutting priorities. The move to a system of shared missions guiding the most recent (BCC, 2025b) plan was developed with One City partners, all thematic boards, and over 200 stakeholders via the City Gathering and other forums—alongside input from the Bristol Advisory Committee on Climate Change, the SDGs Alliance, the Youth Council, and citizens and colleagues across the city. These governance structures formed the institutional backdrop for Bristol's CCC: six climate action pathways structured around a 2030 roadmap, an investment plan, and a commitment to reflexive monitoring and learning. Developing the CCC involved cross-departmental working, the NZC-inspired Transition Team model to support multi-sector coordination, and technical assistance from NZC consortium partners.

Community Level: The Community Climate Action Plans

All 17 CCAPs underwent an intentional multi-stage journey. CAO leaders began by building their climate knowledge: understanding the local and national policy context and generating a community carbon footprint. They then built an initial priorities snapshot via pre-engagement (surveys, door-knocking), before delivering a series of inclusive engagement events to gather insights and develop community ownership of priorities. Priorities were structured across seven climate action fields, co-developed with partners and refined with local stakeholders, climate experts, and decision-makers to ensure feasibility and strategic alignment. Final CCAPs were shared widely to catalyse implementation and lever practical, financial, and strategic support. Support mechanisms were integral: a capacity building programme matched CAO leaders across cohorts; roundtable events brought community, city, and regional stakeholders together to surface connections between CCAPs and existing or prospective initiatives; and the Community Leadership Panel provided a channel for community insights to inform city and regional strategy.

The 17 CCAPs were the product of extensive co-production by community leaders with deep local knowledge, trusted relationships with residents, and a diversity of participation formats and venues. Analysis of the plans identified patterns consistent with city strategies (covered in [Brief 2](#)): variations in applications of the CCAP impact framework co-benefits within individual CCAPs and across organisations; activity and/or output indicators used where impact indicators were expected; and the relationship between co-benefits is often implied rather than defined.

While there is further room to develop CAOs' understanding of impact evaluation, these patterns reflect the difficulty of operationalising an emerging co-benefits framework in a context of no established UK standards for community-based co-benefits approaches, alongside capacity constraints CAOs face individually and collectively developing monitoring systems. This further highlights the gap and need for shared monitoring infrastructure – and raises a wider question of where this sits (community, city, regional, or national) and whose responsibility it is to develop and deliver it.

Fields of Climate Action: Related but Not Aligned

At the level of sectoral coverage, the CCC and the CCAPs share common ground. Both address Built Environment and Energy, Mobility and Transport, Green Infrastructure, Waste & Circular Economy, and Just Transition priorities through identified climate mitigation and adaptation actions.

Yet when placed side by side, they reveal a common urban climate governance challenge: structural misalignment. The colour-coded fields-of-action comparison ([Figure 6](#)) makes these overlaps visible—and shows where community priorities diverge from city-level strategy.

Figure 6. Bristol CCC and CCAP Fields of Action. Own Illustration.

Overall, both represent attempts to operationalise just transition principles and integrate mitigation and adaptation, but they were developed through separate processes with different definitions, metrics, and theories of change. The result is two parallel visions of what just transition looks like in Bristol—one at city scale, one at community scale.

The most promising areas to build upon are identifying where priorities under the CCC's 'Just Transition Engagement & Skills' pathway and the CCAPs' 'Community Engagement/Supporting Conditions,' 'Business and Skills,' and 'Other/Leadership Development & Equity' fields can be aligned to be mutually reinforcing.

Impact Frameworks: Parallel Rather Than Integrated

The complexity of structural alignment across impact frameworks becomes clear when comparing the three used across Bristol's Net Zero Investment Co-Innovation lab ecosystem (shown in Figure 7). All three were developed through separate funding streams and for different audiences: the CCC emerged from the NZC ecosystem; the CCAP Impact Framework

co-developed by CCA Project partners with National Lottery funding; and the CCA Prospectus Social Value Impacts (BCNP, 2025a) developed with investor audiences in mind. Taken together, these emergent approaches provide valuable insight into the similarities and differences of city- and neighbourhood-level priorities and theories of how change is expected to unfold.

Figure 7. Bristol CCC, CCAP Impact Frameworks, and CCA Social Value Impacts. Own Illustration.

This is not a failure of ambition or technical capacity—it reflects the structural reality of project-based funding and differing requirements. These innovative processes create similar but parallel theories of change that cannot easily be compared, aggregated, or used to generate collective intelligence about what is working and why. Without shared monitoring systems, the feedback loops between community and city-level governance that Bristol's Just Transition in Action Model calls for cannot be fully realised.

As shown in **Brief 2**, this misalignment is not unique to Bristol—it is a structural feature of

urban climate governance more broadly, reproduced wherever governance tools are developed within governance networks (NZC, NZL, C40, etc.) without explicit alignment mechanisms and methods. Addressing it requires deliberate investment: in joint framework development, in shared impact taxonomies, and in the monitoring and learning infrastructure that can hold city and community-level theories of change in productive dialogue. This is a prioritised area of work as the community empowerment work goes regional (WECA, 2025a) and will be an important area of further research.

Bridging the Gap: Co-Benefits, Community-Led Values, and the Path to Integration

Placing the CCC and CCAPs side by side reveals not just a framework integration challenge but a deeper governance tension: the gap between co-benefits ambition and practice is not primarily technical—it is institutional, relational, and political. Cities are caught between competing logics: a carbon and investment logic that demands measurable, monetisable outcomes; and a social and justice logic that demands inclusive, equity-oriented processes. Bridging these logics requires governance innovation across multiple dimensions—and sustained investment in the relational 'people work' that makes it possible. This is examined in more detail in **Brief 4**.

Analysis of the CCAPs reveals that community-led climate action strongly prioritises social and environmental co-benefits—with Health & Wellbeing, Society, and Environment impacts dominating—while carbon impacts are framed as means to community benefits rather than primary goals. This 'top meeting bottom' reframing demonstrates the distinctive contribution community-led approaches can have to articulating what a just transition looks like at street level.

At the same time, the CCAPs reveal real limitations that mirror those seen at the city levels. Impact pathways are often conflated with actions; definitions of co-benefits vary widely

across organisations; and there is no systematic monitoring infrastructure to aggregate or compare impacts across the 17 plans. The most important co-benefits for communities—social cohesion, mental health, sense of agency, community resilience—are precisely those that are hardest to measure and least likely to be tracked in city-level or global reporting systems like CDP. This is not a failure of ambition; it reflects the structural gap between what community-led governance prioritises and what existing monitoring architectures and methodologies can capture.

The path to genuine integration finding ways for formal city systems and informal community-led practices to be complementary. This means building shared co-benefits languages that can hold community-level and city-level theories of change in dialogue; designing monitoring systems that make the non-monetisable outcomes of just transition governance visible; and creating governance mechanisms—like the Bristol Community Leadership Panel (BCNP, no date b)—that are designed to give community knowledge real influence in high-level decision-making rather than adding it as a consultative layer. **Brief 2** reveals the systemic measurement gaps that make this bridging work so difficult. This brief shows what Bristol's 'first next steps' toward advancing it in practice look like.

What's Next in the Series

This is **Brief 3** of the NZF Series, summarising the doctoral thesis of Joel Terwilliger: **Towards More Participatory Net Zero Futures (2022-2026)**, supervised by Ian Christie, Stelvia Matos, and Subhes Bhattacharyya. The next titles in the series are: (**Brief 4**) *Governing Net Zero Missions: Innovation, Alignment, and Mobilisation Insights from Bristol and Fellow Cities*; and (**Brief 5**) *Missions, Myths, and Contemporary Procedural Governance Tools: Reflections and a Proposed Research Agenda*.

KEY INSIGHTS & POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

For Mission-Minded Cities and Practitioners

- Use the Four-Lens Model as a diagnostic before launching new governance initiatives—asking whether proposed interventions attend adequately to institutional, market, community, and systems perspectives simultaneously, and where the greatest misalignments lie.
- Resource the Bridging role. Supporting citizens to change is not a soft add-on but a core governance function requiring dedicated capacity for active alignment of strategic and investment planning with just transition principles.
- Build a shared theory of change and identify key joint metrics wherever possible. In the absence of a national framework, deliberate co-design with city, community, and investor partners — including early engagement with trade-offs as well as areas of collective action potential — is essential.
- Build explicit feedback loops from community plans into city strategy. Mutual city-community influence requires intentional governance that systematically brings community priorities, local intelligence, and co-benefits evidence from CCAPs into CCC review, investment planning, and policy cycles.

For Policymakers

- Establish a National Net Zero Community Action Framework. VCSEs surface priorities—resilience, social inclusion, wellbeing—that city and regional planning systems struggle to absorb: existing monitoring systems lack the methods to define and scale just transition metrics. A consistent impact taxonomy and monitoring guidance would help bridge that gap, enabling community-defined value to genuinely inform city and regional strategies without losing local specificity.
- Recognise the VCSE sector's governance role in governance frameworks. Trusted CAOs are co-producers of climate governance, not delivery vehicles — a relational ecosystem that must be resourced and maintained.
- Name and resource the hidden cost of enabling governance. The facilitation, brokerage, and framework-alignment work that makes just transition governance function is routinely treated as an absorbed overhead. National programmes should explicitly account for these costs and ring-fence resources accordingly.

- Use Bristol's model as the basis for a statutory duty for net zero. Translating grant-funded innovation into a statutory requirement—with associated resourcing—would enable frontrunner approaches to inform national delivery at scale.

For Funders

- Build incentives for existing framework holders and designers to collaborate rather than compete. Funders should encourage alignment between existing frameworks before supporting new ones, and encourage work toward shared impact infrastructure. Most decision-support tools remain largely conceptual and disconnected from practical city needs; co-refining existing tools with cities would serve the field better than producing new ones with low uptake/usefulness.
- Fund the maintenance and embedding of ecosystem gains. Plan refreshes, peer learning, and relationship maintenance are the conditions under which innovation investments retain value — they do not sustain themselves once project funding ends.
- Connect ecosystem processes to community-shaped investment—taking a programme rather than project view of co-investment, built on the equitable city-community partnerships Bristol's CCC-CCAP alignment work has demonstrated.

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